

Secure Image Indexing Using Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF) Key Points and SHAKE256 Hashing

Mohammad Awad Alfawair, Khalid Alkaabneh

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 03, 2021

Accepted:
August 07, 2021

Keywords :

Development, Internet
And Storing Data,
SHAKE256

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5168797

Abstract

Due to the rapid development of the Internet and storing data, several security attacks have taken place, causing deep fears to computer users. On the other hand, many computer users mainly depend on different techniques to protect their data and keep them safe and secure, including their private images, since they are important and sensitive. Some currently applied procedures do not provide enough protection for the privacy of the stored images. Consequently, researchers are exerting great effort to search for images in a more secure way using different codes. The primary purpose of this thesis is to solve the issue of data security to reduce the chance or possibility of losing these images. A procedure has been introduced to search for images more safely to be restored safely depending on the content of these images themselves. Also, this suggested technique helps provide more image privacy and the ability to search for these images more accurately. In addition, using the index will inevitably lead to more privacy for stored data. Based on my thesis, I recommend we use the SURF Algorithm to define the essential image points m , we use the OTP Algorithm to increase the security level, and finally, we apply the SHAKE256 algorithm for more security. Thus, the highly-secured search is provided, and precise control of reaching these images and restoring them is enabled. The approach that I recommend has been tested in this thesis using MATLAB Pack, which is very effective. Then, the findings of the test were tested using 100 images from the database of Stanford University. Those images were classified into four groups: animal images, people and faces, nature, and buildings and terrain. The results showed that the images that have more points are more secured and highly protected. Another criterion, about the number of zeroes and ones of the image, has been applied to the results to provide more security and protection. I also implemented two criteria to test the security level using the same findings. These two criteria are the number of zeroes and ones and the change in the image itself. As a result, I concluded that when the number of zeroes is equal to the number of ones, this shows a high level of image security. In conclusion, my research findings indicated that implementing the suggested approach to protect images is more effective than other previous researches.

Introduction

Today's world is witnessing a massive advancement in technology usage, and hence security became one of the essential concerns because of the increasing cybercrime making data security insufficient, security provided to images, where the use of photos has increased exponentially. Facebook users had uploaded over 250 billion photos, with a daily 250 million increase in photos (Bohari and Raeen, 2013).

The number is increasing dramatically with features like automatic downloading from cell phones to insecure areas like I-cloud. In addition, users search for images in the public cloud and outsource them as it is an economical choice for many organizations.

In addition, some images may contain compassionate information; external sources that may have been used for the search may raise privacy concerns. Researchers are trying to make several attempts to search for images more secure and, more specifically, via an encrypted data set, but this may affect the accuracy or efficiency of the search (Yuan et al., 2015).

A method has been suggested to search for encrypted images securely to retrieve them after they are stored on the cloud, relying on the image content via encrypted image databases.

This method helps provide privacy, protection, and the ability to search accurately through encrypted images without decryption, protecting the privacy of the stored sensitive data.

The study technique relies on a secure indexing system that describes resolving data security, and it is considered one step for achieving possible cloud services by providing safe content based on a large-scale image search with fine-grained access control.

The study model will rely on Speeded up Robust Feature (SURF) to extract (64) key points from an image, then using One Time Pad (OTP) to merge a security key with the extracted points; this will raise the security level of hacking the index. Then use a secure hash algorithm called SHAKE256 to produce a unique, irreversible index used to search the image.

Researchers are seeking to develop approaches that help extract points from images more accurately, better and faster. There are several approaches used to detect and match features as SIFT (Scale Invariant Feature Transform), SURF (Speeded up Robust Feature), FAST, ORB, etc. (Mistry, D., & Banerjee, A.,2017).

(De,1999) has proposed an algorithm called SIFT, and after applying it to a large number of images, it was found that it requires a long time in the electronic calculation which is much slower in implementation, and thus scientists needed to develop a suitable reagent and descriptor in terms of a balance between speed and accuracy (Zahedi, M., & Eslami, S.,2011).

As a result, in 2006, Bay, T. Tuytelaars, and L. Van Gool proposed an algorithm called SURF that made online calculation robust and nearly twice as fast way as the sift algorithm(Bay, H., Tuytelaars, T., & Van Gool, L.,2006, May).

SURF algorithm is the most helpful approach to detect and match the features because it is invariant to scale, rotate, translation, illumination, and blur (Karami, E., Prasad, S., & Shehata, M.,2017).

In this thesis, the SURF algorithm is used in the proposed approach because the SURF algorithm is better than the SIFT algorithm for hard, camouflage, and warp conversion. SURF is three times faster than SIFT due to the use of an integrated image and square filter. SIFT and SURF are good at changing photo brightness (Mistry, D., & Banerjee, A., 2017).

SURF algorithm is a more useful and a better choice than the Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) (Ahmad, K., Ahmad, N., KHAN, R., Khan, J., REHMAN, A., & HASSNAIN, S., 2013).

Comparing the SURF algorithm and the SIFT algorithm is not that important because it has been proved to us previously that the SURF algorithm is much better and more effective than the SIFT one. Thus, the SURF algorithm has been implemented.

One Time Pad (OTP) will be used to merge a security key with the extracted points; this will increase the level of security of penetration of the indicator. One-time pads figured prominently in secret message transmission and espionage before and during World War II and in the Cold War era. On the Internet, the difficulty of securely controlling private keys led to the invention of public-key cryptography (Glover, 2005).

Messages encrypted with keys based on randomness have the advantage of theoretically no way to "break the code" by analyzing a succession of messages. In cryptography, A One-Time Pad is a system in which a private key generated randomly is used only once to encrypt a message that is then decrypted by the receiver using a matching one-time-pad and key (Margaret Rouse.,2005).

SHA-0 is 160-bit hash function published in 1993 under the name "SHA". It was withdrawn shortly after publication because of an undisclosed "significant flaw" and has been replaced by the slightly revised version SHA. A cryptographic hash function takes an arbitrary block of the input string and returns a fixed-size bit of output string. The cryptographic hash values differ due to any accidental or intentional change to the data (Sahu and Ghosh, 2017).

A secure hash algorithm called SHAKE256 will be used to produce an irreversible unique index that will be used to search for the image; it is considered the best encryption algorithm for the SHAKE256 hash technique since it is the best in terms of speed and collision rate (Sahu and Ghosh, 2017).

1.1 Research Problem

The study problem stems from the importance of data security since huge amounts of money were spent on data protection from any external penetration. With the ever-increasing amount and variety of data stored and transmitted in various mediums, the specification of security which has to be established at multiple levels has become a critical factor (Abraham, A., & Paprzycki, M.,2004, April).

According to a survey conducted by IDC in 2009, 74% of IT and IT managers believe security issues are their primary challenge. In another survey carried out by Gartner in 2009, more than 70% of CTOs believed that there are data security and privacy concerns (Chen, D., & Zhao, H.,2012, March).

Through the use of images that have been widely published on the Internet, the useful content in the images is searched for, and in general, it is an economical and flexible option for many institutions. However, many images contain sensitive and private information, but image search services outsourced to the public raise privacy concerns. As a result, researchers make several attempts to protect data and images, search for them safely through encrypted data, and focus on retrieving these images safely and quickly.

1.2 Research Questions

The study attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the best (fast & accurate) scientific way to extract image properties?
2. How to enhance the performance of data security and increase the safety of the index?
3. What is the best algorithm that can be used for hashing to produce zero collision and a unique index?

1.3 Research Objectives

This thesis contains several objectives:

1. Reach the best scientific method for extracting the characteristics of the image using the SURF algorithm because of its many advantages, including the extraction of about (64) points in record time and the required accuracy.
2. Increase the ability to perform information security by narrowing the image at several stages to make it difficult for the hacker to view information content, protecting its details using the OTP algorithm and the hash application.
3. Use the SHAKE256 hash technique since it is considered the best in terms of speed and collision rate (Sahu and Ghosh, 2017).

1.4 Limitations

When designing an efficient and secure image search system on encrypted data sets, there are some challenges: search efficiency, search accuracy, and access control. Specifically, the optimal search map for the secure image must have an encrypted data set with close and accurate search efficiency to search in a clear data set that relies on extracting data from the integrated clear images. Since the coded indexes allow the comparison of similarities to enable the staged restoration of images, one of the possible attacks from the server is to compare all the images in the database until the similarity information is obtained between the images.

In addition, the server's information similarity can be determined during the loopback process because similar images will be returned based on the user query image. However, since all the data queried in the encrypted database, the information similarity alone will not help the server infer the content of the image. In addition, there were some obstacles that this study encountered regarding sources:

1. Lack of sufficient resources and research in this area and the location of data storage on the Internet.
2. Lack of data protection, as this field, is relatively new, and generally, there is no adequate and nutritious study to protect the data, and later the researcher will test several results to clarify the working method by showing results.

1.5 Research model

Figure (1) Model Description

1.6 Significance of the Research

With the growth of data and the importance of safe searching for images in large data sets, as photos may contain information that is very sensitive because of privacy, researchers strive to maintain confidentiality and security very effectively and focus on different areas, including data sharing.

This study proposes to protect the images stored on the server or the Internet while providing a safe environment to preserve the privacy of information, including images by encrypting them in several stages, as well as speeding up the process of searching for them and accessing a wide range of content, with an opportunity to search for the required images accurately. By analyzing the image's content (using the SURF algorithm) and creating a unique index for each image, the desired image can be searched and retrieved; this helps the users increase their work efficiency, as the study contributes to using a method of securely recovering images on a large scale, faster, and with high privacy.

The indexed database, based on image analysis by SURF (content-based search), is intended to provide accurate search by index. Advances in this area help to protect the privacy of stored data. It is considered necessary to protect the service provider's privacy and potential intruders (Lo et al., 2009). In a safe recovery scenario, search indexes must be correctly created and encrypted by user-side toolbars using a secret key (Lee et al., 2018) for certain content to be recovered from the image database.

By using the image database, the focus is on building security search indexes that protect the privacy of image content and maintain resilience in the shortest time until the image is retrieved more quickly.

1.7 Procedural Definitions

1.8.1 Extract Features

One or more attributes represent the process of extracting features from the image, such as shape and color, to distinguish images based on content and features during the image retrieval process.

The query features are compared to the image in the database (Choras, 2007). Extracting features is important because the specific attributes presented to differentiate the effectiveness of the compilation task directly. The final result of the extraction task is a set of features (Choras, 2007).

1.8.2 Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF)

Standard to detect points of interest and descriptive characteristics, surpassing other standards in terms of frequency, excellence, and durability, can be calculated and compared faster; this is achieved by relying on integrated images; to build strengths in detectors (using a Hessian-based matrix to detect and a description based on distribution) and detecting definitions and matching steps. The standard evaluation set showed some of the image experiments applied to the context of object recognition, and SURF offers strong performance (Bay et al., 2006).

Figure 2 shows the use of the SURF algorithm to discover points of interest in the Lena image. (Voila Jones, 2005).

Figure (2) Points of interest in the image after applying the SURF

1.8.3 A One-Time Pad (OTP):

In cryptography, A One-Time Pad is a system in which a randomly generated private key is used only once to encrypt a message decrypted by the recipient using a one-time key. The messages encrypted through the keys based on randomization have the advantage. Theoretically, there is no way to "break the code" by analyzing a successive series of messages. Each encoding is unique and disassociated with the next encoding until the same patterns can be discovered. With a One-Time Pad, however, the decrypting party must have access to the same key used to encrypt the message, which raises the problem of getting the key to the decrypting party safely or how to keep both keys secure.

One-time pads have sometimes been used when both parties started out at the same physical location and then separated, each with knowledge of the keys in the one-time pad. The key used in a one-time pad is called a secret key because if it is disclosed, the messages encrypted with it can be easily deciphered. One-time pads figured prominently in secret message transmission and espionage before and during World War II and in the Cold War era. On the Internet, the difficulty of securely controlling secret keys led to the invention of public-key cryptography (Glover,2005).

How OTP Works

Typically, a one-time pad is created by generating a string of characters or numbers that will be at least as long as the most extended message that may be sent. This string of values is generated in some random fashion - for example, by someone pulling numbered balls out of a lottery machine or using a computer program with a random number generator. The values are written down on a pad (or any device that someone can read or use). The pads are given to anyone who may be likely to send or receive a message. Typically, a pad may be issued as a collection of keys, one for each day in a month, for example, with one key expiring at the end of each day or as soon as it has been used once.

When a message is to be sent, the sender uses the secret key to encrypt each character, one at a time. If a computer is used, each bit in character (usually eight bits in length) is exclusive "OR'ed" with the corresponding bit in the secret key. (With a one-time pad, the encryption algorithm is simply the XOR operation. There is some concern about how truly random the key is; it is sometimes combined with another algorithm such as MD5). One writer describes this kind of encryption as a "100% noise source" used to mask the message. Only the sender and receiver have the means to remove the noise. Once the one-time pad is used, it can't be reused. If it is reused, someone who intercepts multiple messages can begin to compare them for similar coding for words that may occur in both messages.

Figure 3: Shows how to use the OTP algorithm for the encryption process by adding a password.

One-time Pad: Encryption

e=000 h=001 i=010 k=011 l=100 r=101 s=110 t=111

Encryption: Plaintext \oplus Key = Ciphertext

	h	e	i	l	h	i	t	l	e	r
Plaintext:	001	000	010	100	001	010	111	100	000	101
Key:	111	101	110	101	111	100	000	101	110	000
Ciphertext:	110	101	100	001	110	110	111	001	110	101
	s	r	l	h	s	s	t	h	s	r

Figure (3) the OTP algorithm for the encryption process

1.8.4 SHAKE256 Hashing Technique:

SHA-0 is 160-bit hash function published in 1993 under the name "SHA". It was withdrawn shortly after publication because of the undisclosed "significant flaw" and replaced by the slightly revised version SHA. A cryptographic hash function is a hash function. It takes an arbitrary block of the input string and returns a fixed-size bit of output string. The cryptographic hash values differ due to any accidental or intentional change to the data (Sahu and Ghosh, 2017).

Applications Functions of hash message authentication have been used to check if a message has been modified. Digital signatures: encrypt digest with a private key, Key storage, digest of the key is compared with that in the storage; hackers cannot reach a key from the storage. Key generation: key can be generated from the digest of pass-phrase; it can be made computationally, but it is expensive to prevent brute-force attacks. A pseudorandom number of generation iterated hashing of a seed value. Intrusion detection and virus detection; keeping and checking the hash of files on the system (Stallings, 2002)

The hash processor can execute a new hash algorithm, SHA-3, and extendable-output function (XOF), SHAKE-256. The processor that consists of a padded block, round-core block, and output block maximizes its performance using the block-level pipelining scheme. The padded block formats the variable-length input data into multiple blocks, and then the round block generates the SHA-3 message digest or SHAKE256 result for multiple blocks using the on-the-fly round constant generator. Finally, the output block transfers the result to the host processor. The hash processor is the estimated maximum throughput is 5.28 Gbps (gigabits per second) for SHA3-512. Because the processor supports both the SHA-3 hash algorithm and the SHAKE256 algorithm, it applies to cryptographic areas such as data integrity, key generation, and random number generation (Beena and Benish, 2018).

1. Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF)

It is a detector and a constant meter even if there is a rotation or any change in the image. It means the object can be selected even if the image is enlarged or the image border around the axis of representation is changed in an image. The discrepancy occurs because of how the information exists; stability is essential to the characteristics identified and recognized, where the measurement of similarity is in the features that distinguish the image from others and do not change.

The algorithm starts by extracting the main points within the images, which are considered acceptable in creating a representation of an image content description. The algorithm then calculates the key points detected and calculates the lengths as increased image descriptions, which increases accuracy (Kumar and Batra, 2011).

SURF is the fastest algorithm compared to other algorithms (Bay et al., 2006) since the algorithm depends on the descriptor based on specific characteristics after the extraction of the complexities are classified

compared to other algorithms. After that, the proposed prototype is subject to several phases, including orientation and extraction. The stages are executed through SURF descriptors. When these stages are completed, they are grouped as sections, and the graphs are created (Bay et al., 2006).

A One-Time Pad (OTP):

In cryptography, A One-Time Pad is a system in which a randomly generated private key is used only once to encrypt a message that is decrypted by the recipient using a one-time key, where the messages are encrypted through the keys based on randomization. It has the advantage, which is theoretically impossible to "break the code" by analyzing a successive series of messages. Each encoding is unique and not associated with the following encoding until the same patterns can be discovered (Glover,2005).

The OTP is known as an unbreakable cryptosystem that Shannon proved in 1949. The key length in the OTP is the same as the message length, and The 2016 IEEE INFOCOM International Workshop on Mobility Management in the Networks of the Future World 978-1-4673-9955-5/16/\$31.00 ©2016 IEEE. This key is only used once. Gilbert Vernam first invented this cryptosystem for telegraph communication in 1917. And currently, many modern cryptosystems utilize this method for securing communication, such as Quantum Cryptography(Katz, J., Menezes, A. J., Van Oorschot, P. C., & Vanstone, S. A.,1996).

Hash Function

Hash function (H or HASH) produces a different code for each additional input, a collision-free function. The Hash function provides a fixed size output code regardless of the size of the input text. Furthermore, the distribution of change is very random on the resulting text, so that changing only one bit in the input text produces an entirely different code than the original script, which makes a valuable hash in data integrity. This function is called a cryptographic hash function (Saarinen, M. J. O., 2014, February).

The cryptographic hash functions are one-way algorithms that are invariably non-reversible (where their potential is much greater than the efficiency of the brute force attack); HASH features can be summarized as a collision-free product of fixed size code for each input and non-compute. Because of these characteristics, hash functions are often used to determine whether or not data have changed. Constantly, the inputs are padded to a fixed size (e.g., 512 bits) to increase the attacker's difficulty of predicting the original text and then performing operations that produce text representing the HASH code for the input. There are many HASH functions such as MD5, SHA1, SHA256, SHA384, and SHA512 (Saarinen, M. J. O.,2014, February).

The "Strict Avalanche Criterion" (SAC)

This feature is one of the criteria for measuring the security of the algorithm key. In this criterion, the number of zeros and the number of units are calculated in the ciphertext of the key, and if the number of zeros is equivalent or close to the units and their distribution is organized within the key, then it will become difficult to break, which provides us with a higher level of protection. (Castro et al.,2005).

The "Bit Independence Criterion" (BIC)

All of the security of such cryptographic algorithms depends on the strength of the key, where a new security test for the key bit independence criterion (BIC) test is considered a security criterion where its proximity has zeros measurement after the coding process. Whenever the spacing is significant zeros, it is difficult to break the key (Sheng, Wenping, & Jiwei, 2011).

Remote Server

The device can control but to a certain degree via the Internet, whether in a building or even another country.

When protecting the privacy of the data, the images are encrypted before being transferred to the remote server using one of the encryption methods in the remote server, searching for similar images and extracting the encrypted images related to the query image (Lu et al., 2009).

2.2 Previous Studies

Saini et al. (2014) mentioned that information retrieval is an important research area in computer science and engineering as the retrieval of information is primarily concerned with the exploration and retrieval of data expected from the database. It has been concluded that information retrieval is the process of searching and retrieving knowledge-based information from a wide range of documents.

Velmurugan and Baboo (2011) mentioned that Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) is a difficult task based on retrieving images or similar databases. Most CBIR use low-level features such as color and shape to extract features from images. Points were previously used to remove the most similar images from different perspectives. Their work, SURF, is combined with the color feature to improve the accuracy of the loopback. SURF is fast and a detector of valuable points in use, and it is used in many computer vision applications. It is required to work on images that are always grayscale, to improve the performance of the SURF color, KD-Tree is used with the Bin First Best Search algorithm (BBF), which indexes and matches the similarity of image

features and the use of the voting scheme algorithm, in the end, to arrange and retrieve identical images from the database.

It was also concluded that the massive growth in image data leads to the need for searching and retrieving images, as the retrieval of images based on content is very important in research and multimedia databases.

The combination of SURF and color has been achieved by improving the accuracy of the system recovery by 23% of the average precision Velmurugan, K., & Baboo, L. D. S. S., 2011).

Lu et al. (2009) stated that retrieving information and maintaining data confidentiality and privacy is an important matter that all researchers seek to achieve. If a database is stored on a server, it is maintained by external tasks. In addition, the primary purpose of retrieving information via an encrypted database is a right that must be provided for accurate access to documents that have been encrypted without decryption. The emerging field of business related to securing the multimedia recovery process, including images, is a safe process that aims at an outstanding performance while maintaining confidentiality and privacy.

The focus here is on recovering the content of the encrypted multimedia database. An image database was used as an example where the focus is on creating secure search indexes that protect the privacy of the server's image content and maintain the ability to compare and retrieve faster and better.

Chora (2007) mentioned that the various widely used computer applications are the recovery process of the required images from a large set based on the features that can be automatically drawn from the same image as these systems are called CBIR (Content-Based Image Retrieval). This system has received extensive attention to the non-retrieval of information for images. These algorithms are usually divided into three functions: extraction, selection, and classification.

The restore task converts content from images to different features. Feature extraction is the process of generating features to be used in the selection and classification process. Feature selection reduces the number of features provided for the classification process, as these features are likely to help in discrimination, and they are selected and used in the classification task and exclude features that are not selected.

The feature extraction process is critical because the features available for the discrimination process directly affect the effectiveness of the classification function, and the result of the extraction is a set of features.

(Kaabneh, 2007) suggested new indexing techniques for content-based queries in image databases and mentioned that indexing is the key to provide sophisticated, accurate, and fast search queries in data types. This indexing is based on the linear modeling of signals using rules for modeling. The new indexing relies on the linear modeling of signals using modeling rules. The base is a set of selected images, and image modeling approximates the lower squares of the image as a linear combination of essential images. The basic image coefficients are taken together to serve as an index of that image as it describes the implementation of the indexing system, where the results of the process of implementation of this system significantly increased the efficiency of performance.

The OTP is known as an unbreakable cryptosystem that Shannon proved in 1949. The key length in the OTP is the same as the message length, and The 2016 IEEE INFOCOM International Workshop on Mobility Management in the Networks of the Future World 978-1-4673-9955-5/16/\$31.00 ©2016 IEEE this key is only used once. Gilbert Vernam first invented this cryptosystem for Telegraph Communication in 1917. And currently, many modern cryptosystems utilize this method for securing communication, such as Quantum Cryptography (Katz, J., Menezes, A. J., Van Oorschot, P. C., & Vanstone, S. A., 1996).

The cryptographic hash functions are one-way algorithms that are invariably non-reversible (where their potential is much greater than the efficiency of the brute force attack). HASH features can be summarized as a collision-free product of fixed size code for each input and non-compute. Because of these characteristics, hash functions are often used to determine whether or not data have changed. Constantly, the inputs are padded to a fixed size (e.g., 512 bits) to increase the attacker's difficulty of predicting the original text and then performing operations that produce text representing the HASH code for the input. There are many HASH functions such as MD5, SHA1, SHA256, SHA384, and SHA512 (Saarinen, M. J. O., 2014, February).

2. Methodology

Image protection is based on extracting features for each image, encoding, encrypting, storing, and saving, comparing the index of the required image with all the images stored in the vast database, and retrieving the required images through its index.

Knowing that the images are encrypted increases privacy and protection and help protect sensitive data for the stored content.

3.1 The Proposed Methodology

3.1.1 The Proposed Technique

The technology inserts images one by one. Each image decomposes and extracts the number of points highlighted in it using the SURF algorithm. After extracting the highlighted points within the images, the points are encrypted by another algorithm, and thus difficult to retrieve the image.

When a user wants to search for an encrypted image, he or she enters the index number of the image, which was created by the proposed approach in and accordingly, the desired image is retrieved.

The main idea in this proposed approach is to use the SURF algorithm to detect the number of points in all images and then to use the OTP algorithm as an additional layer to increase the security level to penetrate the index and to apply the SHAKE256 algorithm to increase the level of security better. It also provides secure image search and precise access control, which increases the protection and privacy of the images.

Figure 4: model represents the steps of a safe image secure system

3.1.2 Algorithm: Model Steps:

Input: Image.

Output: Index of Image.

1. Read the image file.
2. Extract the points of interest from each image through the application of SURF points 64.
3. Convert each point to a binary number.
4. Combine the result (combine all previous numbers representing all points extracted to become one binary number).
5. Implement the OTP algorithm by adding a 64-bit key to static for all images, converting it to a binary number, then applying the XOR process with the last number.
6. Implement SHAKE256 secure hash to produce a unique index (N), by entering the last number.
7. Send and save the index (n) for the image.

3.1.3 Hardware Specifications:

The proposed approach has been applied to an HP type; the CPU specification is i7, plus 8GB of RAM and a 1TB hard disk.

3.1.4 Implement Matlab:

MATLAB is the application software for the fourth generation and the numerical analysis environment. This program includes matrix calculations, development and operation of algorithms, user interfaces, and data visualization. It is usually used with experiments in the image process provided (Rajan and Fred, 2017).

There are different versions of MATLAB. This paper uses MATLAB 9.4.0 (released February 23, 2018) called R2018a; this release includes new versions of MATLAB and Simulink, with new graphical and Simulink controls, which are not available in earlier versions.

3.1.5 The Dataset

A variety of image sets was used within the Stanford University database, which contains 9907 images. One hundred of which were chosen to test the proposed approach, if it achieved outstanding results, means its success on most of the pictures, and then divided them into four groups (Animal Pictures, People & Faces, Nature, Buildings & Terrain) to compare them. Each set contains 25 images (as shown in Table 1); each image is set to 4 bytes and a JPEG image type.

Table 1: Dataset

No.	Group Name	Class Image	No. of Images
1	Animal		25
2	People & Faces		25
3	Nature		25
4	Buildings & Terrain		25
Total			100

3. Results and Discussion

This section outlines the results of implementing and testing the proposed approach.

In the process of protecting images in a way that is based on the image analysis algorithm and then encrypting the index for preserving the image and keep it

In 2017, Mistry, D., & Banerjee, A. mentioned that the SURF algorithm is the most helpful way to detect and match features because it is consistent in scaling, rotating, translating, lighting and blurring. SURF is three times faster than SIFT due to the use of an integrated image and square filter.

In 2013, Ahmad, K., Ahmad, N., KHAN, R., Khan, J., REHMAN, A., & HASSNAIN, S. mention that the SURF algorithm is most useful and is the best option compared to SIFT conversion.

In this research, the SURF algorithm will apply it to the proposed approach because the SURF algorithm is better than the SIFT algorithm. After all, comparing the SURF algorithm with the SIFT algorithm is not rewarding because it is known and proven that the SURF algorithm is better than the SIFT algorithm for conversion, fluxing, and transformation. Through the research mentioned above and at the beginning of the paper. The idea was to apply the results through the surf algorithm as it is the proposed approach.

The image protection process goes through several stages, from analyzing all images to their distinctive elements using the SURF algorithm and then adding a key them using the OTP algorithm and the SHAKE256 algorithm and then storing the index, after which the images are retrieved by querying them through their index and following the same steps and comparison, this increases privacy and protection.

4.1 Experimental results

When testing the model, the proposed methodology was applied to a diverse set of images from within the Stanford University database, which contains 9,907 images, 100 of which were chosen to test the proposed approach.

In addition, all experiments were completed using the Matlab program through programming required by following the flow chart steps mentioned in the previous chapter.

100 photos were divided into four main groups; each group contains 25 pictures:

- Animal.
- People & Faces.
- Nature.
- Buildings & Terrain.

By applying the proposed methodology to the images, the number of points extracted from the images was calculated and compared to it, as shown in the results later.

4.2.1 Results based on the implementation of the SURF algorithm, in the first set of images, **Table 2** shows the results of the number of points extracted from animal images using the SURF algorithm.

Table 2: Results of the number of points extracted from animal images.

Image No.	No. of Points
1	22
2	37
3	18
4	48
5	69
6	26
7	56
8	31
9	33
10	23
11	14
12	27
13	45
14	35
15	23
16	23
17	48
18	25
19	28
20	50
21	30
22	55
23	35
24	13
25	58
Avg.	34.88

The results showed that the first group that contained animal images was among the highest images in terms of the number of points extracted through the SURF algorithm, as shown later in **Figure 5**, this may attribute to animal pictures containing many details, which increase the possibility of getting more points than them, which confirm their better protection through the proposed approach.

4.2.2 Results based on the implementation of the SURF algorithm, in the second set of images, **Table 3** shows the results of the number of points extracted from images of people and faces using the SURF algorithm.

Table 3: Results of the number of points extracted from images of people and faces.

Image No.	No. of Points
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26	48
27	39
28	32
29	36
30	33
31	53
32	32
33	17
34	45
35	10
36	18
37	32
38	39
39	27
40	41
41	22
42	18
43	54
44	44
45	44
46	25
47	65
48	34
49	13
50	19
Avg.	33.6

The results showed that the second group that contained images of people and faces was among the highest images in terms of the number of points extracted through the SURF algorithm, as shown later in **Figure 5**, this may be because the images of people and faces contain many details, which increases the possibility of extracting more points from them and confirming their better protection through the proposed approach.

4.2.3 Results based on the implementation of the SURF algorithm, in the third set of images, Table 4 shows the results of the number of points extracted from nature images using the SURF algorithm.

Table 4: Results of the number of points extracted from natural images.

Image No.	No. of Points
51	38
52	28
53	22
54	61
55	27
56	36
57	24
58	61
59	10
60	30
61	14

62	61
63	10
64	30
65	20
66	56
67	20
68	17
69	12
70	39
71	11
72	10
73	54
74	21
75	38
Avg.	30

The results showed that the third group that contains the nature images was the lowest in terms of the number of points extracted through the SURF algorithm, as shown later in **Figure 5**, this may be because the images of nature contain few details. However, the difference in the number of points extracted from the rest of the groups is insignificant, confirming their better protection through the proposed approach.

4.2.4 Results based on the implementation of the SURF algorithm, in the fourth and final set of images, **Table 5** shows the results of the number of points extracted from building and terrain images using the SURF algorithm.

Table 5: Results of the number of points extracted from building and terrain imagery.

Image No.	No. of Points
76	28
77	8
78	13
79	34
80	34
81	15
82	42
83	53
84	12
85	85
86	46
87	24
88	13
89	9
90	35
91	72
92	12
93	62

94	62
95	56
96	53
97	21
98	32
99	34
100	35
Avg.	35.6

Finally, the results showed that the fourth group that contains the buildings and terrain images was the highest in terms of the number of points extracted through the SURF algorithm, as shown later in **Figure 5**, this may be because the images of nature contain the most significant number of details, which increases the possibility of extracting more points than that, which confirms their better protection through the proposed approach.

4.3 Results based on the average

When the proposed method for four groups of images was tested using the Surf algorithm to discover the number of points extracted for each image, we calculated the average number of points extracted for each group. The results were shown in **Figure 5**: all images are extracted from Many points, which helps to protect them by applying the proposed approach.

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average number of points extracted

Figure 5: Results of Average number of points extracted from the images for each of the four groups

4.3.1 Results based on an examination of the level of protection on the first group photos. **Figure 6** shows the number of zeros and ones and the amount of change resulting from images of animals using the proposed approach.

Figure 6: Results of several zeros ones and the amount of change extracted from the images of the animals.

The results show in **Figure 6** that the first group that contains the images of animals was equivalent and close in terms of the number of zeros and ones and the amount of change. According to the criterion of "Strict Avalanche Criterion" (SAC) that if the number of zeros and ones is close or equivalent in the ciphertext of the key, and organized within the key, then it will become difficult to break, which provides us with a higher level of protection. And this proves and confirms the increased safety of the images through the previous results.

4.3.2 Results based on examination of the level of protection on the second group photos. **Figure 7** shows the number of zeros and units and the amount of change resulting from images of people and faces using the proposed approach.

Figure 7: Results of several zeros and ones and the amount of change extracted from the images of people and faces.

The results show in **Figure 7** that the second group that contains the images of people and faces was equivalent and close in terms of the number of zeros and ones and the amount of change. According to the criterion of "Strict Avalanche Criterion" (SAC) that if the number of zeros and ones is close or equivalent in the ciphertext of the key, and organized within the key, then it will become difficult to break, which provides us with a higher level of protection. And this proves and confirms the increased safety of the images through the previous results.

4.3.3Results based on examination of the level of protection on the third photo group. **Figure 8** shows the number of zeros and ones and the amount of change resulting from the nature pictures using the proposed approach.

Figure 8: Results of several zeros and ones and the amount of change extracted from the images of nature.

The results show in **Figure 8** that the third group that contains the images of nature was equivalent and close in terms of the number of zeros and ones and the amount of change. According to the criterion of "Strict Avalanche Criterion" (SAC) that if the number of zeros and ones is close or equivalent in the ciphertext of the key, and organized within the key, then it will become difficult to break, which provides us with a higher level of protection. And this proves and confirms the increased safety of the images through the previous results.

4.3.4Results based on an examination of the level of protection on fourth group images. **Figure 9** shows the number of zeros and ones and the change resulting from images of buildings and terrain using the proposed approach.

Figure 9: Results of several zeros and ones and the amount of change extracted from the images of the building and terrain

The results show in **Figure 9** that the fourth group that contains the images of buildings and terrain was equivalent and close in terms of the number of zeros and ones and the amount of change. According to the criterion of "Strict Avalanche Criterion" (SAC) that if the number of zeros and ones is close or equivalent in the ciphertext of the key, and organized within the key, then it will become difficult to break, which provides us with a higher level of protection. And this proves and confirms the increased protection of the images through the previous results.

3.4 Results of the average amount of change when testing the four image groups. Based on the proposed method for calculating the amount of change for each set of images, the results appear as shown in **Figure 10** that the average amount of change between the four image groups was high. This confirms that the spacing between zeros is significant, as the key is difficult to break, providing a higher protection level, and this proves and confirms the increased image protection according to the "Bit Independence Criterion" (BIC) standard. All of the security of such cryptographic algorithms depends on the strength of the key, where a new security test for the key bit independence criterion (BIC) test is considered a security criterion where its proximity has zeros measurement after the coding process. Whenever the spacing is significant zeros, it is difficult to break the key; this proves that the proposed approach protects all images. **Figure 10** illustrates the graphical representation of the average change columns for each group of images using the suggested method.

Figure 10: the average amount of change for each set of images.

4. Conclusions and Future Work

This section summarizes the conclusions of the experiments on a set of images; the use of the SURF algorithm. In addition, it explains the future work that develops the results of the study.

5.1 Conclusions

In this paper, image protection is increased to enable easy retrieval by analyzing images with the SURF algorithm based on image content analysis as they have been applied to about 100 images. The results were better for the images with more points extracted and the amount of change in all images; proving this, this allows the user to protect the images further.

5.2 Future Work

This shows that work might be applied to the cloud and test the ability to encrypt and protect images on the cloud and not hack based on the specific criteria mentioned above. In addition, two algorithms can be used to analyze the image's content, which increases the protection of the images.

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Author Information

Mohammad Awad Alfawair

MA. Student, Amman Arab University, Jordan

Prof. Khalid AlkaabnehProfessor, Faculty of Information Technology, Al-Ahlyya Amman University, Jordan
